

POLICY BRIEF

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INTEGRATED OCEAN GOVERNANCE: ELEMENTS AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCES

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POLICY STATEMENT

In the 1980s, with the technological evolution for the exploration of the marine environment and implementing the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, new concepts of sovereignty and rights of sovereignty over maritime areas were introduced. Thereby, many countries started to think about the marine environment strategically apart from their terrestrial environment and consider the maritime security issues in their public policies. In the past, maritime security issues were focused exclusively on the maintenance of maritime trade in wartime. Nowadays, marine resources exploration and management of the maritime environment in times of peace can be added. Furthermore, in the XXI century, there are multiple maritime security concepts outlined by diverse actors, not only security and defense departments. This multiplicity of voices ends up in different forms of actions, sometimes aligned, sometimes conflicting, but rarely efforts with an integrated conception. One of the most common approaches division of maritime security concept would be safety actions or security actions. Topics related to safety can be highlighted, such as marine search and rescue, certification and inspection of ships, protection of the marine environment, elaboration of navigation rules, all related to the guarantee of navigation and human life. This approach is related to actions done without the "use of force." On the other hand, topics related to security are related to activities done with the possibility of the "use of force" to secure or defend people, goods, equipment, ships, and installations. However, this division presents difficulties in delimiting actions to combat criminal activities at sea, even in countries like Brazil where the Navy is at the same time the Maritime Authority, responsible for the safety, and the actor which projects seapower, being accountable for security.

BACKGROUND

This background briefly presents how complex it is to combat criminal activities at sea for countries or even international organizations, mainly due to the need for permanent mapping of threats at sea (promoting the Maritime Situational Awareness). For the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO)¹, Maritime Situational Awareness (MSA) is defined as "the understanding of military and non-military events, activities and circumstances within and associated with the maritime environment that are relevant for current and future NATO operations and exercises." In this Policy Brief, I propose that Maritime Situational Awareness is the primary key for an Integrated Ocean Governance supported by actions of multiple actors (civil or military; public and private; local, regional or global). Governance is something that is part of the mainstream of public policies in the 21st century. Many analysts use the European Union's supranational governance in several fields to present elements that should compose multi-agency public policies. In the same way, the September 11 terrorist attacks justified, among other factors, by the existence of gaps in integrated security, led the US government departments to design governance systems of multi-agency to reduce costs, share information, and build trust.

There are diverse forms of multi-agency governance, focused on a specific theme with agencies from various states with legal competence and permanent structures for this theme, or even with internal agencies with different responsibilities that act in an intersectoral and intergovernmental way. Furthermore, governance is a multifaceted and complex process for marine environmental management, involving a wide range of stakeholders from numerous institutions and individuals with different interests, agendas, and sets of skills. Several barriers exist for states [or their departments] to work together on securing their shared coastal and marine ecosystems, with discussions often becoming clouded when disputes arise over Exclusive Economic Zones, borders, oil and gas resources, continental shelves, maritime transport, and fisheries². In most cases, it is observed fragmented governance frameworks. In other words, actor A analyzes the situation collecting data, makes its agenda, and sets its skills; actor B does these steps on its own, and actor C does the same. Besides that, rarely, there is a similar methodology employed. The zone of analysis can be local, regional, or global, and the selection of stakeholders may be different. The mapping tools used can be diverse and not integrable, or the approach and the actors can only be based on safety or security.

FINDINGS

In some countries, in addition to policies and strategies for the sea, action plans for integrated ocean governance have been outlined, primarily focused on surveillance or exchange of information, as an example, the United States that from 2004 have created plans that propose a high level of interagency cooperation to achieve an effective awareness and management of the maritime environment. These plans bring together civil and military government agencies (federal, state, and local) and the private sector in a layered proposal. In this integrated ocean governance by a layered proposal, the USA has the National Maritime Intelligence-Integration Office (NMIIO) to integrate data and generate knowledge about the maritime environment from multiple stakeholders. Another experience of integration of systems among public authorities would be the Common Information Sharing Environment (CISE). CISE aims to make European and its member states maritime surveillance systems interoperable, enabling all concerned authorities to exchange information automatically and securely. The initiative operates in the following sectors: safety and security of maritime transport; fisheries control; marine pollution preparedness and response; protection of the marine environment; border control; general law enforcement and defense. CISE is composed of expert representatives of the EU countries and the European Union agencies such as the European Defence Agency (EDA), the European Fisheries Agency (EFCA), the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex), European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)³. Specifically, the EMSA was established in 2002 to support the EU in the maritime safety and prevention of pollution from ships, and subsequent amendments have refined and enlarged its mandate⁴. The Agency nowadays integrates multiple technological marine space management systems such as radar, satellites, drones, AIS, LRIT. Finally, Brazil's experiences of integrated ocean governance contribute to the safety and security of the South Atlantic, as inside the Maritime Area of the South Atlantic (CAMAS) framework. This experience is an information-sharing instrument about maritime traffic control composed by Brazil, Argentina, and Uruguay. Second, the Brazilian Navy has marine space management systems.

The most important one is the Maritime Traffic Information System (SISTRAM), which processes merchant ships and fishing vessels data inside Brazil's maritime area of responsibility and data from Brazilian flagships or chartered by Brazilians, anywhere in the ocean.

The SISTRAM is supplemented with data from the *Programa Nacional de Rastreamento de Embarcações Pesqueiras por Satélite* (PREPS) and *Sistema de Monitoramento Marítimo de Apoio às Atividades do Petróleo* (SIMMAP). Besides that, Brazil permanently created an architecture, in 2018, called the Integrated Maritime Security Center (CISMAR), aiming to contribute to the safety and security of Brazilian maritime traffic interest, to fulfill commitments related to Maritime Traffic Naval Control and the Naval Cooperation and Guidance for Shipping (NCAGS). The Brazilian maritime situational awareness is relatively efficient with this structure. However, these experiences also have a very restricted field to data processing and collection by military stakeholders.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

As Admiral João de Faria states, all this compilation of information covering environmental data (oceanography, meteorology, and others), ship positions and features, transported cargo and logistics chain, regional activity patterns, fishing zone, trade routes [...] highlights the depth and complexity of information about the maritime domain, being notorious that it extrapolates the collected data by the sensors of the Navy [...]⁵. So, it can be pointed out that the elements for an integrated ocean governance must be listed and structured in permanent standard networks or architectures in real-time. Networks or architectures that bring together civil or military, public and private, local, regional or global actors: these conditions allow the creation of a communication channel to exchange information and build common doctrines and trust. For the future, Brazil is planning a system that should be a real practical experience of integrated ocean governance inside the Brazilian Jurisdictional Waters (AJB), an architecture that can bring together civil or military; public and private; local, regional or global stakeholders. The Blue Amazon Management System (Sistema de Gerenciamento da Amazônia Azul - SisGAAz) will also feature data from some other systems. Still, it will make it possible to increase the capacity of monitoring, analyzing, and merging large volumes of data, even if data from different sources and forms. Not only it permits the collection of data, but it can integrate this to bring forth knowledge/awareness, supplanting the perspective of having only disconnected information. It is not an easy task, mainly due to the scientific and technological limitations of infrastructure and economic resources restriction. The SisGAAz will be a service system⁶, an architecture for collecting and exchanging information through a monitoring system (surveillance); management system (command and control); communications and interoperability system; and protection system (safety and security approach), structured with the proposal of outlining a standard macro process of doctrines, norms, and procedures for stakeholders, whether facilities, organizations or people.

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